

Functional Outcome of Management of Distal Humerus Fracture Treated with Pre-Contour Extra-Articular Humerus Plate

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Abstract

Fractures of the distal humerus in adults represent about 2% of all fractures and make up a third of humerus fractures. These injuries are particularly challenging due to their location near the joint, the small size of the distal bone fragments, and the reduced bone quality in older adults. This study aims to assess the clinical, radiographic, and functional outcomes of using a pre contour extra-articular humerus plate for extra-articular distal third humerus fractures, utilizing a posterior triceps splitting approach.

Method: This prospective study was conducted at Jhalawar Medical College, Jhalawar, involving 15 consecutive skeletally mature patients with closed extra-articular distal humerus fractures. These fractures were treated using a pre contour extra-articular humerus plate, and the outcomes were evaluated based on radiological evidence of healing, functional results, and any complications that arose.

Result: The use of a pre contour extra-articular humerus plate resulted in predictably high union rates and excellent patient outcomes without any implant-related complications.

Conclusion: We recommend the use of a pre-contoured extra articular plate for these humerus fractures due to its consistent results in fracture union, stability across the fracture site, and the facilitation of early mobilization, leading to better functional outcomes.

Keywords: Humerus Fracture, Fracture Fixation, Pre-Contoured Extra Articular Plate.

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Introduction

Fractures of the distal humerus in adults constitute about 2% of all fractures and one-third of humeral fractures [1,2]. There is substantial evidence indicating an increase in the global incidence of distal humerus fractures [3,4]. For males, the incidence declines with age until the seventh decade, while in females, there is a slight decrease between the second and third decades, followed by an increase with age [5]. High-energy trauma, such as roadside accidents and sports injuries, accounts for most fractures in young patients. In middle-aged and elderly females, fractures typically result from simple falls, where the elbow is either directly impacted or axially loaded during a fall on an outstretched hand. [5,6]

Fractures of the distal third of the humerus present significant challenges due to their location near the joint, the small size of the distal bone fragments, and the osteopenic quality of the bone in older adult [7]. Management methods for distal humerus fractures include conservative approaches such as plaster cast immobilization or the use of a

functional brace, fixation with plate and intramedullary nailing. [8,9,10]

Although conservative treatment of these fractures can result in satisfactory union, operative treatment is often preferred due to the risks of radial nerve injury during closed reduction or movement of the fracture ends, difficulty in controlling fracture alignment, and the potential for elbow stiffness after conservative treatment. [11-14]

The posterior approach provides better exposure of the distal third humerus fractures, allowing for optimal visualization of the radial nerve. Most experts recommend using a 3.5 mm low-contact dynamic compression plate (LC-DCP) with 3.5 mm diameter screws, ensuring purchase of 6 to 8 cortices on either side of the fracture. [14-16]

Several authors have recommended centering the plate on the shaft to manage distal humerus fractures [17-20].

Moran identified this issue and suggested using an anterolateral approach to the distal humerus. [21].

The aim of our study was to assess the clinical, radiographic, and functional outcomes of using a pre contour extra-articular humerus plate for extra-articular distal third humerus fractures via a posterior triceps-splitting approach.

Method

This prospective, hospital-based study was conducted at Jhalawar Medical College, Jhalawar from April 2022 to August 2023. Patients were selected from those who visited the emergency and outpatient departments. Approval was obtained from the institute's ethical committee, and written informed consent was secured from all patients or their families.

The study included FIFTEEN skeletally mature patients (with fused epiphyseal plates around the elbow) who presented to the orthopaedics department with fresh extra-articular distal third humerus fractures

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients with extra-articular distal humerus fractures (AO type 2 and 3)

- Age group between 19 and 65 years.
- Patients presenting with closed fractures less than three weeks of injury.
- Grade I open fractures, according to the Gustilo-Anderson Classification.

Exclusion Criteria

- Individuals younger than 19 years or older than 65 years.
- Patients with intra-articular distal humerus fractures.
- Open Grade II or Grade III as per the Gustilo-Anderson Classification.
- Presence of metabolic bone disorders or pathological fractures.
- Underlying neuromuscular disorders.
- Patients deemed unfit for surgical intervention.
- Patients unwilling to provide consent.

In all 15 cases, we used the 3.5 mm pre-contoured extraarticular locking compression plate for extra-articular distal humerus fractures, and the posterior triceps-splitting approach was employed in each case. (figure1)

Figure 1

The patient was positioned in the lateral decubitus position with the arm supported on a padded bar to allow elbow flexion. (figure 2)

Figure 2

In the immediate post-operative period affected arm immobilized in a U slab, the patient's general condition and fluid balance were closely monitored. Antibiotics were administered according to hospital protocol, and analgesics and other supportive care were provided as needed.

Patients were typically discharged on the third or fourth day, depending on their overall condition, with medications suitable for home use.

Postoperatively sutures along with slab removed in 2nd week, shoulder and elbow range of motion

exercises were initiated within two weeks. Follow-up evaluations were conducted both clinically and radiologically at 2 weeks, 6 weeks, 12 weeks, and 24 weeks.

All patients remained in the follow-up period, which lasted 6 months.

Observation and Results

Table 1: Distribution of Age of Patients

Age	Frequency	Percent
19-35 Years	7	46.7
36-45 Years	3	20.0
46-55 Years	1	6.7
56-65 Years	4	26.7
Total	15	100.0

In the present study, 46.7% (n=7) patients fall in 19-35 age group, 20% (n=3) patients fall in 36-45 age

group, 6.7% (n=1) patients fall in 46-55 age group, 26.7% (n=4) patients fall in 56-65 age group.

Table 2: Distribution of Gender of Patients

Gender	Frequency	Percent
Female	5	33.33
Male	10	66.67
Total	15	100.0

In present study, 66.67% (n=10) patients were male and 33.33% (n=5) patient were female.

In present study, 53.3% (n=8) patients were left-handed and 46.7% (n=7) patient were right-handed.

Table 4: Distribution of Mode of injury of patients

In present study, 73.3% (n=11) patients had history of fall and 26.7% (n=4) had history of RTA.

Table 5: Distribution of AO type of patients

In present study, 53.3% (n=8) patients had A2 type fracture and 46.7% (n=7) patient had A3 type fracture.

Table 3: Distribution of Range of motion of patients (elbow joint)

ROM	Frequency	Percent
>100°	9	60.0
50°-100°	5	33.3
<50°	1	6.7
Total	15	100.0

In present study, 60% (n=9) patients had ROM >100°, 33.33% (n=5) patient had ROM 50°-100°, 6.7% (n=1) patient had ROM <50°.

Table 4: Distribution of Mayo elbow performance index of patients

MEPI	Frequency	Percent
Excellent	8	53.3
Good	5	33.3
Fair	1	6.7
Poor	1	6.7
Total	15	100.0

In present study, 53.3% (n=8) patients had excellent score, 33.33% (n=5) patients had good score, 6.7% (n=1) patient had fair score and 6.7% (n=1) patient had poor score.

Case Illustration

PRE- OP X-RAY

IMMEDIATE POST- OP X-RAY

6 Week Follow Up X-Ray

12 Week Follow Up X-Ray

24 Week Follow Up X-Ray

Clinical Photos

Discussion

Treating distal humerus fractures is particularly challenging. These fractures are often comminuted with long butterfly fragments, occur in osteoporotic bone, and involve complex anatomy, which limits options for internal fixation. While extra-articular humerus fractures can potentially be treated non-operatively with a functional brace, this approach can be cumbersome and difficult for patients

initially. Additionally, it has been associated with issues such as skin problems, malalignment, joint stiffness, and a risk of nerve injury during reduction or fracture mobility.

We treated fifteen patients with extra-articular distal humerus fractures using anatomically pre-contoured extra-articular distal humerus plates. The results from our study were favourable.

Our study included patients with AO/OTA fracture types A2 and A3, with type A2 having incidence of 8 and A3 having incidence of 7. All fractures had united by 24 weeks, both clinically and radiologically, with a mean duration of fracture union of 15.8 weeks.

In comparison, a study by Fawi et al [22]. (2014) reported a mean fracture union duration of 15.7 weeks, while Chowdary et al. [23] (2015) reported a mean duration of 12 weeks. (22,23)

In our study, 9 patients (60%) had a range of motion of 100 degrees or more, and only 6 patients (40%) had a range of motion less than 100 degrees.

15(100%) in the age group of 19-65 years 10(66.67%) were male patients Left side was involved in 8(53.33%) (73.33%) 11patients sustained injury due to road traffic accident.

Functional outcome as per mayo elbow performance score in the present study is excellent in 8(53.33%); good in 5(33.33%); fair in 1(6.67%); poor in 1(6.67%)

In our study, managing extra-articular distal third humerus fractures with anatomically pre-contoured extra-articular humerus plates, combined with early mobilization, resulted in predictably high union rates and excellent patient outcomes. The stability of the locking construct, which provides extra purchase due to the shape of the plate and minimal periosteal compromise, ensures high union rates even in osteopenic and comminuted fractures.

Additionally, a more aggressive rehabilitation approach with elbow mobilization during the first postoperative week should further improve the range of motion and address the issue of extensor lag

Conclusion

Our study has shown outstanding results without any implant-related complications in the internal fixation of extra-articular distal third humerus fractures using a single pre contoured extraarticular humerus plate. We advocate for the use of this extra-articular distal humerus plate for these types of fractures due to its reliable outcomes in terms of fracture union, stability across the fracture site, and facilitating early mobilization for improved functional results.

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